

Public Relations

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The most complex and difficult activity to manage is communication, because even knowing that organizations communicate to different segments of the public, it is necessary to manage communication globally.

However, with social and cultural adaptations, the behaviour of groups within organizations is consolidated and communication, as it is directly linked to the individual and his relationships with others, becomes a specific system that plays a major role for the individual emergence, survival and evolution of organizations.

This makes clear the need for integration and harmonization between all areas of the organization around the "mission", "values", "goals" and "objectives", which should result in a description of the concept that the organization will aim to have with its public.

In the search for a new communication it is essential to note that the progress of telecommunications, the use of ultra-sophisticated methods of storage and reproduction of knowledge, is not enough. It is necessary to rethink each sector, each modality, but analyzing and enhancing communication as a total process.

In all, the dichotomy, theory and practice, is present. It is impossible to analyze, advance, control technologies and resources without taking into account their ethics, operability and benefit to all people in all professional sectors.

A few years ago, organizations' communication managers have come to realize that their main asset is their employees. From then on, internal communication became one of the main strategies in relation to its employees.

Therefore, it emphasizes that the way of planning and managing internal communication is directly linked to the place occupied by communication and professionals in this area in administrations, whether public or private.

The activity of the communicator implies breaking with the isolation of individuals and ghettos, with distrust in the purposes of the leaders and the institutions themselves.

Challenges of the communicators of these institutions internally are to exercise dialogue and direct it towards achieving satisfaction with work, internal coexistence and other personal aspirations.

Therefore, the diagnosis of structural and internal relationship problems allows identifying difficulties, threats, failures and communication opportunities. This identification enables the creation of a communication system appropriate to the

existing culture and, consequently, a management model that guarantees the accomplishment of the institution's mission.

And it is at this juncture, full of peculiarities that the communication professional has to act. Faced with a new geopolitical order, a dynamic, open and competitive market, with new technologies and, above all, with a new organization, based on information, which will enable and supply all this new perspective.

Communication

Man has the great ability to communicate and create. People's ability to interrelate through ideas, the ability to record thoughts and information, and the way each individual or group has to deal with other groups through a communicative process is fundamental to the whole nature of social relationships of the human species.

Communications are basic to the daily existence of every modern individual and every organization, whatever its size. Every organization needs to know what is happening to the groups that influence it and how to reach the various audiences it deals with.

Communication takes place by bringing individuals closer together and, consequently, by strengthening human and social relations, where these individuals seek to satisfy their common needs and interests, mediated by interaction practices, mutual cooperation and collective actions.

Structured by common interests and values, the dynamics of social and cultural formations occur through ways of identifying and conflicting relationships, causing the consolidation or segregation of groups and / or individuals.

Regardless of the outcome, such oscillations reinforce the characteristics of each social grouping and stimulate the emergence of specific communication systems that sustain the growth and reproduction of human culture with its particular values.

With this, organized and instituted social groupings develop relationships of reciprocal obligations and compensations, creating a life in society. And so, communication develops in this society as one of the main tools for social, cultural and organizational learning.

Organizational culture is defined as a set of beliefs and values specific to a given organization, that is, habits, mentality, leadership style, behaviours and standards adopted by the organization that create a unique identity towards others.

In this perspective, communication is used to preserve this identity or to be the instrument that drives desired transformations, since organizational communication comprises the entire message flow that makes up the organization's network of relationships.

Today, the communication sector is changing due to the different challenges brought about by globalization processes, especially in the beginning of this century, where communication activities and practices begin to function as strategic areas between nations economic, social and political development.

Therefore, the figure of the Public Relations is projected in this scenario of growth, having to gain space in the territory of the intermediate entities of society. Its mission is to plan and operate strategies and consistent positions for closer relations of society.

It is a competence that will enable him to rise to the level of strategist and thus perform higher functions, extrapolating his interference in the environment of the organization and making him a political agent in building a society more aware of rights and duties.

Communication in Organizations

When organizations or people talk about communication, they must be clear that communicating is much more than talking well, writing well, being nice or having charisma.

Communication is also planning, clearly defining objectives and contributing to the unity of all members of the organization in relation to them. It is to have preferential messages that guide the discourses of all of them in the search for the coherent transmission of these messages.

When organizations or companies talk about communication, they should think about conveying a planned message that is coherent with the messages of the past, in accordance with the reality of the present and coherent with the projection of the future, which the company's planning instruments indicate and A communication work should formalize, always with a view towards what concept the organization wants to have with its public .

Today, changes have been occurring rapidly, making organizations continually assess which direction they want to go and what actions are needed to get there. This is the biggest challenge an organization faces, unity of thought, from the shop floor to top managers, everyone's effort needs to be directed towards the same goals and actions must be consistent with the values that the organization stands for.

Within an organization, communication always occurs, whether planned or not. Society reads and evaluates companies and their managers in relation to their physical presence, their management models, organizational structures, their human resources, policies and relationships with countless audiences.

Today, modern companies speak for themselves, through their facilities, about the behaviour and style of their executives and employees; These are all transmitters of positive or negative signals and it is all of these requirements that also contribute to building the image of an organization.

The communication process is the most complex factor of modern administration, by the huge and intricate network in which it develops. The organization gains a lot from the work of a communication department, as competition in a world where technological and innovation differentials in any field quickly disappear.

The emphasis is then on communication, in the strategic management of it in an integrated and cohesive manner, making the company differentiate itself from its competitors.

Therefore, communication in organizations can no longer be viewed by business managers as merely a technical and tactical tool, but as a strategic and permanent tool

Common Profile of the Social Communicator

Media professionals should follow a common profile, because it is this profile that ensures the identity of the course as being Communication, and that characterizes in general components of the profile of professions in the area, such as Journalism, Advertising and Advertising and Public Relations.

The Public Relations professional, besides the common components to the communication field, is characterized by:

1. By managing the relationship of organizations with their various audiences, both external and internal, through communication strategies;
2. For the elaboration of diagnoses, prognoses, strategies and policies aimed at improving the relations between institutions, organized human groups, sectors of public or private activities and society in general;
3. Working on the implementation of programs and instruments to ensure this interaction, monitoring, evaluating and refining the relevant processes and products based on the results obtained;
4. Working with public or private institutions that include activities characterized in terms of communication strategies whereby those institutions may develop interactions with relevant interlocutors;
5. Interlocution between the typical public relations functions and the other professional or business functions

Communication, as well as other social, cultural and economic areas with which public relations interface;

6. For the performance of all other activities which, in the current state of the profession, are recognized by common sense, representative entities or relevant legislation as characteristics of the Public Relations professional.

Therefore, the conception of Public Relations is broad, its foundation is complete and involves the entire organizational process. According to current legislation, public relations activities are not subordinated to any other area or segment within the structure of an organization and considering this responsibility is the fulfilment and commitment of these professionals to follow the code of professional ethics, which establishes fundamental principles for the exercise of the profession.

Fundamental duties of the Public Relations professional:

- a) Strive for maximum efficiency in its services, always seeking to be updated in studies of the Media and other areas of knowledge;
- b) Take responsibility only for tasks for which he is capable, recognizing their limitations and giving up work that may be harmed by them;
- c) Collaborate with Public Relations professionals' training courses, namely in counselling and guidance for future professionals.

The Public Relations professional is prohibited to:

- a) Use any method, medium or technique to create unconscious motivation that by depriving the person of their free will, they take responsibility for their actions;
- b) Divert for their own private service, for profit, clients that have served due to their technical function in various organizations;
- c) Support persons illegally practicing the profession of public relations;
- d) Disseminate false or misleading information or permit the dissemination of news that cannot be substantiated by known and demonstrable facts;
- e) Admit practices that may lead to corruption or compromise the integrity of the communication channels or the exercise of the profession;
- f) Disclose false information about the organization it represents.

The Public Relations professional should strive to achieve his or her goals by acting on the macro view of organizational functions and their entire relationship universe, as

well as clearly defined values that permeate the entire structure of the company. It is your duty to make everyone aware, within the organization, of their role and responsibility for their concept.

He supports guides and advises all areas of the organization as to the most appropriate way to conduct their relationships with the public.

The public relations professional is responsible for presenting the good image of an organization, seeking to promote effective communication between the company and its employees, customers, media and society.

He is able to act as advisor and consultant to institutions, formulating a marketing policy society, as well as event planning.

For the Public Relations, its ability to communication and expression will be decisive, as will the ability to manage interests and controversies.

Specific public relations activities concern:

- a) Guiding the heads of public or private institutions in the formulation of public relations policies;
- b) Promoting greater integration of the institution in the community;
- c) Informing and orienting opinion about the high objectives of an institution;
- d) Advising on the resolution of institutional problems that influence the position of the entity before public opinion;
- e) The planning and execution of public opinion campaigns;
- f) External public relations consultancy with the heads of institutions;
- g) The teaching of specific disciplines or techniques of Public Relations, officially established.

Others attribute more characteristics to the Public Relations professional, highlighting his performance in various types of organizations, be they business, governmental, associative, among others. Its activities consist of:

- Plan, implement and evaluate the communication process in organizations with their audiences;
- Design specific and targeted channels of communication within an institutional nature, where messages are not intended only to sell goods and services, but to allow viewing of the organization as a whole;

- Be responsible for the production of informative material, organization of events, opinion polls;
- Develop planned actions, supported by research in systematic communication and programmed participation, seeking to raise the level of understanding, solidarity and collaboration between an entity and its social groups, in a process of interaction of legitimate interests, to promote its reciprocal development and the community to which they belong;
- As a 'mediator of public controversies' you should seek, through ideas and concepts, to establish attitudes and opinions resulting from debates on controversial topics of public interest.

Faced with daily difficulties, it is up to the Public Relations professional to look for new ways and / or discover new fields of action.

Therefore, creativity combined with information exchange can bring new perspectives to the same product or service. It is necessary to observe this same situation from other perspectives, open to all trends, always aiming to add values to the organization.

In some cases the crisis works in favour of public relations. Euphoric customers who made large investments in advertising are beginning to perceive and face the market more carefully. They discover that each niche market needs to be worked on in a different way, wiping out spending, planning activities and targeting specific PR tools for each target audience.

Another sector in which Public Relations takes a leading role is industries. Its function becomes important because it is the PR that must establish a partnership relationship with the community where the industry is installed. This is because public opinion appears, grows and takes root where the industry has its facilities and it is from these roots that privileges and good reception to the industry may arise, or restrictions and lack of support.

A community relations program can bring benefits to the industry.

It progresses with the satisfaction and moral lifting of its employees due to the better living conditions in the community.

A good relationship between organization and community and vice versa prevents the community from constructing and conveying a misconception of the organization. This type of action facilitates the sale of products and / or services, ultimately bringing progress to the industry with the consequent progress and expansion of the community.

This Public Relations policy, as it develops an industry responsibility to the community, generates jobs and job dividends, encouraging community movement and good pay.

These actions also help in the economic future of the place, where possible the company buying in the locality, generating a greater understanding of the work of the industry, maintaining good relations with the press and public opinion leaders, providing teaching assistance and increasing community culture.

The organization of local charity campaigns and civic projects are also worthy of support, as well as the participation of community class associations.

With regard to Public Relations activities with government agencies, due to their natural complexity, these bodies have their image crumbled before public opinion and this is due to the variety and specialization of actions, the geographical dispersion that covers projects, the territorial dimension of the country, the absence of criteria governing the government's media policy and the personalise of some offices, which often promote people rather than facts.

Communication needs to open streams of communication with society:

'The act of communication shall not end with the passing of acts of the government to public opinion.

It is important to know what segments Social leaders are thinking of the government. In this sense, a project of democratic communication must incorporate the sentiments of public creating communication flows that can lead to government society's expectations are important from a control aspect – this is, the government will know how its projects and actions are being received - while allowing to adjust programs.

Government communication policy should detect facts that are news and deserve to be conveyed, select socially significant events, and place government work above personal vanities and interests.

The Public Relations professional should participate in high level discussions, knowing how to interpret the problems that affect a particular audience. He will be the spokesman between the two parties, will take management decisions to the public and will bring the public's view and hopes to the leaders.

At this moment it is crucial that organizations, especially government agencies, understand what communication is for, using it in a manner that is appropriate for the tranquillity and serenity of the citizen, thus seeking a planned and transparent link between government agencies and the population.

Public Relations need to take on a new role, with a new weight and new possibilities, synchronizing projects, performances and communication. The Public Relations

department needs to be directly involved in the areas of press, communication, research, shareholder contacts, financial relations, product promotion, and communication with employees and especially in government relations.

It is essential to know the internal audience in depth through personal contact, in which a relationship of trust is established, learning to listen.

A break in this relationship of trust will mean that the work of communication does not develop, as it is common for companies to assume that they already know their internal public.

Knowing means knowing your yearnings and frustrations, your ideals and your interests and from this information the organization can define its communication program.

Planning the forms of internal relationship is fundamental. It is noteworthy that it starts by segmenting and prioritizing the common interests between the institution and its public, thus facilitating development and establishing consensus around the organization's mission, objectives and purposes.

Accurate and expertly organized information is important when it comes to overcoming obstacles. Thus, there are certain aspects that, in order to make good decisions, should be considered: the pre-establishment of what, who and when, as well as the support of managers and an evaluation plan to measure the progress of what is being done being executed.

Also the relationship with the internal public requires the establishment of appropriate global planning and communication strategies.

With regard to overall planning it is important that all sectors of the organization have commitment to organization and cohesion around common objectives and it is up to planning to identify these needs.

These actions allow teams to work to resolve potential conflicts.

In relation to communication strategies, when appropriate and well designed, they can broaden the range of options in defining, establishing commitments and adding employees. Informal communication can contribute to:

1. Detect nonverbal signs of confusion, satisfaction or exhaustion, joy or sadness;
2. Make alliances identifying who can help, how and why;
3. Define what can and cannot be done;
4. Establish trading strategies and check which points can and cannot be negotiated;

5. Propose actions to those opinion forming servants;

6. Strengthen positive perceptions, which are, spread more and better about good things.

The key to the success of organizations with their internal audiences is that they have a quality communication process whereby information flows intensively from the company's top management to the shop floor staff, and vice versa.

Without a policy of enlightenment, respect and integration, an institution's employees can become a powerful negative force towards the company. The problem of prestige and friendliness of the organization rests mainly on the trust that employees have in your company. Striving to analyze, understand and meet the needs of the social man is as essential to the balance and development of the individual as it is to the harmony, cohesion and efficiency of the organization.

Therefore, it is essential to develop a PR policy that develops a climate of broad understanding and understanding between the company and its employees, because establishing this relationship is possible to target the mixed and external public.

Relationship with the Mixed Audience - Investors

The internal audience, as already mentioned, is made up of the employees of an organization at all levels, as well as their families and dependents; The other publics linked to the institution are called external public.

However, there is controversy regarding investors (shareholders), suppliers and intermediaries (distributors and resellers). Some Public Relations scholars often place these types of audiences in the internal category, as they have close relationships with organizations and in their manifestations resemble internal public relations.

However, it should be noted that these species also have characteristics of external public. Thus, it would be more interesting to classify them as mixed.

One of the most important investor relations Public Relations tools is the annual report, which should be a one-year record of the company's activities and the performance of its management.

Thus, this communication vehicle is public in nature and should not be confused with mere monotonous administrative reports, they must disclose with transparency all information about the administration, even at unfavourable times, periodically present reports and balance sheets, always communicate calls for capital, stock splits, dividend payments and balance of the portfolio, to communicate possible changes, benefits to

employees, in short, to pass the information to account and justify the investment made.

Relations with the Mixed Audience - Suppliers

With suppliers something similar happens with what happens with dealers, with only one difference.

While resellers, by their characteristic functions, are more inside the company than outside, suppliers enter the company, even though they are outsiders.

They get to know her very well, because this knowledge is part of the business.

Suppliers should be viewed as full-body partners, not as mere cost-cutting mechanisms.

Purchasing is no longer being viewed as a supportive function and is beginning to be seen as a cornerstone of company strategy. Best-practice companies see purchasing as a strategic process rather than a mere cost-cutting expedient.

It should be noted that suppliers, in addition to the supply of utilities or services, can provide the company with valuable information regarding business conditions, price trends, trading practices, advertising suggestions, credit recommendations and many others that could never be obtained through other channels or that would require high prices and a lot of time.

Today, you don't waste so much time waiting to talk to the companies. Today, because there are worldwide suppliers, companies streamline their work by including the Internet as a tool for approaching and displaying possibilities.

Despite the evolution of information technology, visits to suppliers are still very useful for the company's relationship with its sources of supply. In these direct personal contacts, many misconceptions and doubts in the company's dealings with its suppliers will be resolved more effectively and within a climate of mutual understanding and satisfaction.

Relations with the Mixed Audience - Intermediates

Generally the only contact consumers have with manufacturers is through distributors, representatives, dealers and resellers, the first three being wholesalers and exclusive resellers and the last as retailers or simply resellers. Thus, in the eyes of consumers, the set of intermediaries represents the factory itself.

Relations with the External Public - Press

Relations with the press are, among the Public Relations functions, those whose purpose is to acquire and maintain the trust of the directors and collaborators of the various media. In order to achieve this end, there is a need for an intelligence service with all the resources and means necessary to carry out its activities.

Often the press in general is considered to be merely an outreach tool for use anyway, but it is also a public and as such should be addressed.

Relations with the press are more than just a matter of publicity: not only is it a vehicle that companies use to transmit publicity to the public, but it also reflects and expresses public opinion and provides organizations with information about the your audience.

Relations with the press, therefore, entail considerations of publicity as well as contact between the public and the institutions.

It is the good relations with the press in general that allow the company to get more news and comments about its actions and guidelines, thus facilitating the increase of prestige and sympathy of the company with the community.

Only through proper media relations can companies avoid unfounded criticism or false information that every journalist is subject to collecting from information sources.

Contact between the institution and the journalist represents the opportunity to convey accurate information and correct lesser information.

Good press relations are not just the result of the personal friendship of the PR and company directors with writers, reporters and journalists.

The key to good relations is readiness, truthfulness, synthesis, interest in the news and editorial material provided to the press.

Therefore, facilitating access to information should be the policy outlined by the Public Relations professional and remembering that the open door policy is always the best solution.

Relations with the External Public - Community

The community is a group of people who, living in the same region, have the essential characteristics of strong cohesion, based on the spontaneous consensus of its members and translated by attitudes of cooperation, in the face of common interests and aspirations.

In Public Relations, when talking about community relations, some points are essential for a positive result:

1. Do systematic work to get to know the community through surveys, surveys and other means to determine the language of future dialogue;
2. Relying essentially on information provided by staff and families, authorities and community leaders;
3. Use all means of communication, but with emphasis on visits, exhibitions, company publications and commemorations and special events related to the community or company;

The success of the institution - community relationship happens gradually.

Public Relations actions should be developed to bring this public closer together, including the adoption of open-door policy, meetings with community leaders, community-driven information publications, contributions to charities, collaboration with public authorities in the conservation of community facilities, collaboration with class associations, assistance to sports clubs and recreational organizations, commemoration of special events, effective participation of local celebrations and the appointment of members to form the organizing committees to coordinate courses of general interest.

The relationship actions performed by the Public Relations professional aim to transform the close community into a favourable public for what matters to the organization.

Relations with the External Public - Schools

There is a social need to establish relationships between the company and the schools. The public and private institutions of elementary and high school, isolated colleges and universities, institutions, agencies and centres of research, technology and postgraduate, the academic-scientific community, directly or indirectly linked to the objectives should be included in the range of relationship concerns.

First and foremost, companies need to know the number and type of schools in the community, the problems and aspirations of the community in relation to schools and also to get information about the needs of the schools in operation.

The purpose of school relations programs is to reduce the existing problems in the community surrounding the company and should not be aimed at increasing sales. These actions allow greater involvement of employees with social causes, leading to an improvement of the environment in which the company operates and the contribution to education.

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